

Evaluation of General Circulation Model (GCM) cloud vertical structure using data from OMI and the A-train

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Motivation: Evaluate model clouds, focus on cloud vertical structure

- **CloudSat radar: the most detailed information on cloud vertical structure**
 - With MODIS gives cloud extinction profiles
 - Spatial sampling is limited
- **Passive sounders (e.g., OMI and MODIS): daily snapshots, ~2 pieces of information on cloud vertical structure**
 - Can examine assimilated data on daily basis
 - Good sampling for examining monthly, seasonal, or annual time-scales

What do real clouds look like to passive sensors?

□: MODIS- CO₂ slicing
cloud-top

◇: OMI simulated from Cloudsat

△: OMI optical centroid cloud
pressure from Raman scattering

CloudSat/MODIS optical depth profiles

Thin upper deck
over lower deck

Optical depth
peaks in
liquid water
portion of
cloud

Optical
depth
peaks in
ice portion
of cloud

New OMI/MODIS cloud simulator

- Fast (simple) simulation of OMI Raman cloud optical centroid pressure (similar in concept to ISCCP cloud simulator)
- Reflectance-weighted pressure scheme – currently does not properly account for in- or between-cloud scattering/absorption, but could apply correction
- Tested with various cloud overlap schemes
- Can be easily modified for other centroid measurements (e.g., P^2 weighting for O_2 - O_2 absorption)

Single day (13 Nov 2006)
Cloud-top pressure, $\tau > 1$

GEOS-5 has higher cloud-tops, closer to MODIS, very similar spatial features

MODIS 150. 256. 362. 469. 575. 681. 788. 894. 1000. **1:30**
MODIS cloud-top pressure (hPa)

overpass

GEOS4 256. 362. 469. 575. 681. 788. 894. 1000. **3 hr avg**
Cloud top pressure (hPa)

GEOS5 256. 362. 469. 575. 681. 788. 894. 1000. **3 hr avg**
Cloud top pressure (hPa)

13 Nov 2006, optical centroid cloud pressure (OCCP)

GEOS-5 has higher optical cloud altitudes, closer to OMI, very similar spatial features

OMI OCCP (hPa)

overpass

Optical centroid cloud pressure (hPa)

Optical centroid cloud pressure (hPa)

**Single day (13 Nov 2006)
optical centroid cloud –
cloud-top pressure difference**

GEOS-5 closer to OMI/MODIS,
very similar spatial features

overpass

GEOS4

GEOS5

GEOS-5

Use “scaled- τ ” approach of Chou and Suarez to visualize GEOS

CloudSat/MODIS extinction

OMI Cloud OCP Simulator

CloudSat track, 13 November 2006

OMI Raman OCP

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Use “scaled- τ ” approach of Chou and Suarez to visualize GEOS

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CloudSat track, 13 November 2006

OMI Raman OCP

Summary and Current Work

- We developed a fast (reflectance-weighted) simulation of OMI-Raman cloud optical centroid pressure
- GEOS-5 clouds significantly improved over GEOS-4
- More detailed validation of OMI cloud optical centroid pressures with CloudSat
- Compare OMI and GEOS-5 for different seasons, etc.
 - Are we getting a good comparison for the right reasons?
 - How well does model simulate clouds in data assimilation vs. climate (coupled and uncoupled) modes
- We plan to add this to the COSP package that includes cloud simulators for many other instruments